

PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING LIFE INSURANCE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. In addition to the further reform of the national insurance market, the article examines the introduction of life insurance in Uzbekistan and its further development. Also, existing problems and shortcomings in this field were identified, and suggestions and recommendations were made for their elimination.

Keywords: insurance companies, life insurance programs, social protection of the population, gross domestic product, life insurance, bonuses, benefits insurance.

Абстрактный. Помимо дальнейшего реформирования национального страхового рынка, в статье рассматривается внедрение страхования жизни в Узбекистане и его дальнейшее развитие. Также были выявлены существующие проблемы и недостатки в данной сфере, и даны предложения и рекомендации по их устранению.

Ключевые слова: страховые компании, программы страхования жизни, социальная защита населения, валовой внутренний продукт, страхование жизни, премии, страхование пособий.

Introduction.

In the conditions of the current developing global economy, the basis of innovative and socio-economic development of society is human capital, which is considered its decisive force. In particular, guaranteeing strong social protection for every citizen of our country, protecting their health and life through the insurance mechanism serves socio-economic development. It is known from the experience of world practice that life insurance appears as one of the modern and

reliable means of socio-economic protection for the population and is increasingly developing within the financial system of foreign countries.

Today, on the basis of national and foreign experiences, it is necessary to assess the development trends and prospects of the market of life insurance services in our country, to determine the factors affecting the development of the life insurance industry and their level of influence, to find the fundamental problems related to the development of life insurance and to solve them. Developing proposals and recommendations to solve it is undoubtedly the most urgent issue on today's agenda.

Main part.

Today, life insurance is widely used in world practice as a major branch of insurance activity. In developed foreign countries, insurance premiums received for life insurance have a higher weight than insurance premiums received for other types of insurance. For example, the share of life insurance in the volume of the total collected insurance premiums in the USA is higher than 50.0 percent.

In our country, the level of growth of the market of life insurance services can be seen in recent years, but although life insurance premiums have doubled on average in the past years, the overall result is that the share of GDP is 0.1% means that the available opportunities are still not used enough. In countries with developed life insurance, this indicator is at least 2-10%.

In all developed countries of the world, Unit Linked investment insurance products are one of the most popular and popular tools in the market of insurance and investment services, because they are a successful symbiosis of these two areas. According to the foreign practice of life insurance, the share of the life insurance network in the GDP of Eastern and Western European countries and the USA is 2-10 percent. In Uzbekistan, this indicator is 0.04-0.1 percent of GDP. 60% of life insurance contracts in the US are Unit Linked programs. On average, 30-70% of all European life insurance funds belong to this segment. For example, in

Slovakia, the share of Unit Linked life insurance is 1.5 percent of GDP, 30 percent in the life insurance market,

Today, there are unsolved problems related to the development of the life insurance network in Uzbekistan:

- non-availability of life insurance programs with investment content in the national insurance market;

- life insurance with savings is considered one of the easiest and most reliable ways to make long-term investments in the world, but this type of insurance is not implemented in Uzbekistan;

- lack of opportunities for reliable placement of insurance reserves and attractive investment instruments for life insurance companies, underdevelopment of the stock market;

- participation of life insurance companies in the stock market is not ensured, directed to the stock market by life insurance companies new electronic business models are not created when choosing a trading strategy for increasing the volume of investments, their duration and reducing possible risks;

- concern of the population about the unstable economic and political situation. Life insurance is primarily an industry that operates under stable conditions;

- currently there is no mechanism to guarantee life insurance payments in Uzbekistan;

- slow development of the legal framework, existence of contradictions in laws;

- lack of implementation of digitalization and computer programs in the implementation of underwriting in life insurance organizations and, as a result, failure to monitor risks in life insurance organizations;

- failure to introduce a mechanism for resolving disputes between parties and guaranteeing legal protection of consumer-insured interests in the life insurance market.

The development of life insurance in many ways directly depends on the state of the national economy, macroeconomic stability, the world view of people in society, the level of acquisition of economic knowledge, the real income of the population, and the level of inflation. In addition, for the full formation of life insurance, it is necessary to develop and implement economic measures aimed at ensuring its financial stability, including setting the minimum value of the authorized capital of life insurance companies as correctly as possible; the minimum excess of assets over liabilities (solvency margin); adequacy of insurance reserves to fulfill insurance obligations; liquidity indicators of the balance sheet and compliance with the maximum liability norms for one risk.

Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4412 dated August 2, 2019 "On measures to reform the insurance market of the Republic of Uzbekistan and ensure its rapid development" and the "Road" approved by this decision map" defined the tasks of developing long-term, innovative (unit-linked) insurance products in Uzbekistan, creating a voluntary pension insurance system, and establishing a payment guarantee fund in the field.

In order to fulfill these duties, life insurance by introducing new innovative insurance products and developing traditional products in high demand, expanding the volume, types, and quality of insurance services, ensuring access of insurance companies to international financial markets, establishing cooperation of life insurance companies with international rating organizations, digitization of underwriting processes and introduction of computer programs is required in life insurance.

If we look at the 2022 reports of the Insurance Market Development Agency under the Ministry of Finance, we can see that not only the insurance market of Uzbekistan but also life insurance is developing well compared to previous years.

Diagram 1.

Diagram 2.

From the charts above, we can see that over the last 2 years, the share of life insurance in premiums and insurance payments has almost doubled. If we analyze the insurance premiums, according to the reports of December 2021, the share of life insurance was 19%, and according to the results of 2022, this indicator

increased by 5% to 24%. has been The share of life insurance in insurance premiums has also increased to a similar proportion. In December 2021, the share of life insurance in insurance payments was 50%, and within a year, this indicator increased to 58%.

Currently, the legislation of Uzbekistan does not have any mechanism to guarantee payments on life insurance. At the same time, the establishment of the system of guaranteeing insurance payments creates conditions for the rapid development of the market of life insurance services and increases the confidence of the population in life insurance. Another distinctive feature of life insurance, unlike general insurance, is that the premiums paid in it are refundable, that is, the insured event is inevitable. In Accumulated Life Insurance, Whole Life Insurance, Investment Life Insurance, Pension Insurance, large sums are accumulated and they are fully returned with interest. This requires a system of additional guarantees. For this reason,

Conclusion.

The following directions are proposed for improving life insurance in Uzbekistan and bringing it to the ranks of developed countries.

- Development of investment insurance products in all areas of Unit Linked, which has the ability to invest in the creation of innovative insurance products in the life insurance network in Uzbekistan;
- to establish an insurance ombudsman for the purpose of guaranteed and legal protection of the interests of consumers-insured;
- creation of a draft decision on the establishment of a payment guarantee fund and its operation in ensuring the financial stability of insurance organizations;
- creation of additional pension insurance and an electronic calculator for its calculation in order to provide social support to the population and prevent dependency;

- creation of electronic programs in order to improve underwriting policy in insurance organizations;
- implementation of the electronic intermediary internet system in order to create convenience for customers and digitize the industry.

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